

**THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS AND PRACTICAL CONSEQUENCES OF THE
CONCEPT OF CORRUPTION****Bozorova Rozigul Sharofovna**

Bukhara State Technical University

Associate Professor of the Department of Social Sciences and Physical Culture,

Doctor of Philosophy in Philosophy (PhD)

Annotation: This article analyzes the essence of the concept of corruption, its historical and theoretical foundations, negative impact on the development of society, and socio-legal consequences. Also, the negative impact of corruption on public administration, economy, education system, and civil society is scientifically and theoretically illuminated, and modern mechanisms for combating it and international experiences are considered. The study substantiates the important role of legal awareness, transparency, justice, and public control in preventing corruption.

Keywords: corruption, bribery, nepotism, public administration, legal awareness, transparency, justice, fight against corruption, social consequences, economic damage, civil society, rule of law.

Corruption is not a new evil, it has existed since ancient times. Ancient Sumer is recognized as the first state to fight corruption. According to another historical source, the fight against corruption began in the 24th century BC in the city-state of Mesopotamia called Lagash, but unfortunately, all efforts were in vain. In later times, there were also fights against corruption, but some of them ended in vain.

Looking at the meaning of the concept of corruption and its historical roots, the ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle noted: "A person who has achieved power with money seeks to profit from it." In another place, he states that "In any state system, work should be organized in such a way - through laws and other decrees - that it is impossible to allow officials to enrich themselves illegally."

One of the Western thinkers, Charles Montesquieu, interpreted corruption as follows. "It is known from the experience of centuries that a person who has any authority is inclined to abuse it and will continue in this direction until he achieves a certain goal." Bribery, favoritism and injustice are interpreted not only as a social vice, but also as a crime against humanity and conscience.

The ancient Persian state - the Achaemenid Empire - fought against corruption in the justice system by imposing cruel punishments. In particular, the historian Herodotus reports that during the reign of King Cyrus II, the son of Cambyses II, a judge named Sisami was flayed alive for taking a bribe from one of the parties and dragged to his seat, and his son was appointed to this position so that he would not forget which seat he was sitting on when he was in court. After that, not a single case of bribery was identified among the ancient Persian judges. The diptych paintings "The Punishment of Cambyses" and "The Flogging of a Corrupt Judge" by Gerard David, based on this event, are located in the Town Hall of Bruges, Belgium.

Corruption is an extremely destructive socio-political force, as a result of which the national economy is undermined, social inequality deepens, people lose confidence in state authorities, organized crime increases, and spirituality in society begins to deteriorate. Since corruption is inherently destructive, humanity has been fighting against it since ancient times.

The dictionary meaning of the word "corruption" is "correi" - according to Roman law, several participants in one of the parties to an obligation relationship with a single object are understood, "rumpere" - to break, damage, destroy, cancel. Nowadays, "Corruption" (from Latin: "corruptio" - to spoil, to sell for a bribe) is a practice of direct abuse by an official of the rights granted by his position for personal gain.

The following four main causes of corruption can be cited.

1. Personal reasons. Corruption is a “bad” phenomenon, it arises due to the inefficiency of poorly educated and poorly paid officials.

2. Institutional reasons. The main factor in this is the weakness of management. For example, the ineffectiveness of personnel training, accounting and control, the ease of hiring and firing officials, and the lack of confidence in them to stay in office for a long time are factors that encourage corruption.

3. Systemic reasons. The government sometimes faces such demands from society that the formal procedures for their implementation have not yet been clearly developed or they require a large amount of funds and often take a long time. In such cases, direct and short paths to corruption open up.

4. Multifaceted reasons. Sometimes, due to the specific behavior of the state leadership, “personal” factors play a decisive role in state governance. In such conditions, even when trustworthy people are appointed to public positions, corruption increases due to institutional and systemic problems.

The most common types of corruption are considered a vice that holds society back today.

Bribery, that is, taking and giving bribes, This is the most common form of corruption. An official receives material or non-material benefits in exchange for performing a certain service or expediting a legal case. For example, receiving money for passing an exam, receiving benefits in exchange for winning a tender, illegal “collusion” in the courts or law enforcement agencies. From a scientific point of view, in this case, state power serves private interests and legal equality is violated.

The great writer Abdullah Qahhor is one of the writers who sharply criticized bribery, injustice, and abuse of power in his works. He especially exposed the vices of society in his works such as "Thief", "Sinchalak", and "Sound from the Coffin". One of Abdulla Qahhor's famous thoughts close to the content of bribery is quoted as follows: "Bribery is a wound on the body of society." The writer's story "Thief" is also considered one of the works that artistically exposes bribery and social injustice. Also, in the article "Who are the Shroud Thieves?" under the Achti's column, bribery is described as "Shocking a person who has fallen into trouble is like taking off the shroud of a dead person." His comparison deeply reveals how disgusting and inhuman this vice is. Therefore, the works of Abdulla Qahhor still serve as an important spiritual and educational source in the fight against corruption and moral decay.

Fraud is the illegal acquisition of property, money or rights of others by a person through deception, false information or abuse of trust. In jurisprudence, it is included in property crimes and is subject to criminal liability in the legislation of many countries. Scientifically, fraud is interpreted as a socio-legal phenomenon committed on the basis of psychological manipulation, misuse of information, and breach of trust.

One of the main types of fraud is financial fraud, which is the most common type and is aimed at the illegal acquisition of money or material wealth. Its main manifestations include fake investment projects, credit fraud, obtaining money with forged documents, and pyramid schemes. For example, a person collects money from people by promising “big profits”, but in reality the investment does not exist. Financial fraud takes advantage of people’s desire to get rich quick and low economic literacy.

Also, the most common Internet fraud today is (cyber fraud) - a method of fraud carried out through information technologies. There are such types of cyber fraud as Phishing (theft of information through fake links), fake online stores, fraud on telegrams or social networks, and obtaining bank card information. For example, such fraud methods as calling “We are from the bank” and asking for an SMS code are used. Cyber fraud has become a transnational form of crime with the development of digital technologies. Fraud is a complex socio-legal phenomenon, which is closely related to economic gain, psychological manipulation and information technologies. In modern times, especially types of cyber fraud and financial fraud

are expanding. Therefore, in combating it, it is important to: strengthen legal mechanisms, increase digital literacy, develop public control, and strengthen moral education.

Extortion is the act of demanding money, property or other benefits from others by intimidation, pressure, threats or damage to one's reputation. Legally, it is a crime and is considered an act aimed at illegally acquiring property benefits. In scientific and legal literature, extortion is interpreted as: coercive psychological pressure, a mechanism of intimidation, a method of obtaining gratuitous benefits. In this crime, the victim does not act voluntarily, but under fear or pressure. The following can be cited as the main signs of extortion. Threat, that is, pressure by intimidation or harm; Malicious purpose - obtaining money or benefits; Psychological pressure - forcing the victim; Illegal demand - demanding property or services contrary to the law. Extortion is a crime that threatens the security of society, economic stability and human rights. It causes not only material damage, but also strong psychological and social consequences. Therefore, increasing legal literacy, strengthening cybersecurity, combating corruption, and educating young people in the spirit of honesty are important factors in preventing extortion.

Nepotism (nepotism, fraternity) Nepotism is the use of official authority or social status to create unjustified privileges for relatives, close friends, or acquaintances, appoint them to positions, or provide them with benefits.

The term comes from the Latin "nepos" - "nephew", "relative". Initially, this concept referred to the appointment of relatives of religious officials to high positions in the Middle Ages. Currently, nepotism is interpreted as a corruption phenomenon that occurs in public administration, business, education, and other social institutions.

From a scientific point of view, nepotism is considered: a violation of the principle of social justice; the erosion of meritocracy (a system based on qualifications and abilities); a form of institutional corruption; a factor that reduces the effectiveness of management. In sociology, nepotism is interpreted as "placing social ties above professional criteria", and in political science, it is interpreted as the service of state power to private interests.

The main manifestations of nepotism are the appointment of relatives to positions, which is the most common form. For example, hiring a child or relative of a leader without a selection or appointing an unqualified relative to a high position. This situation eliminates professional competition in the organization and reduces the quality of personnel.

Cronyism (friendship) This is not kinship, but giving privileges to close acquaintances, friends or interest groups. The following can be cited as the main manifestations of nepotism. For example, giving tenders to "one's own people", hiring only acquaintances for work, and allowing injustice in promotion. So, if Nepotism is a privilege for relatives, then favoritism or cronyism is a privilege for friends and relatives. Nepotism is not just nepotism, but also a socio-corruptive phenomenon that opposes meritocracy, justice and professional management. It reduces the effectiveness of state institutions, increases corruption and violates the principle of equal opportunities in society. In modern democratic societies, the fight against nepotism is carried out on the basis of: transparency, the rule of law, professional selection, and civil control.

In conclusion, the fight against corruption has been formed on the basis of the legal and institutional experiences of various countries in the historical process. Some countries, in particular Sweden, Singapore, New Zealand and Switzerland, have achieved a sharp reduction in corruption through effective governance, transparency and a strong legal system. These experiences show that although it is difficult to completely eliminate corruption, it can be significantly curbed through strict legislation, political will and public control. Therefore, the experience of these countries is an important practical and instructive model for all societies today.

References

1. Isroilov Bohodir. Explanatory dictionary of terms and expressions related to corruption and the fight against it. Scientific and practical manual. "Tafakkur" publishing house, Tashkent - 2019.
2. Robert Klitgaard - "Controlling Corruption" A classic scientific work on the causes of corruption and its reduction.
3. Susan Rose-Ackerman & Bonnie J. Palifka – “Corruption and Government: Causes, Consequences, and Reform”. Provides an in-depth analysis of the political and economic consequences of corruption.
4. Vito Tanzi – His scholarly work on corruption and public finance examines the economic impact of corruption in public administration.
5. Bozorova, R. (2021, September). Methods and Means of Cultivating Kindness in the Family of the Uzbek People. In " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 43-44).
6. Бозорова, Р. Ш. (2022). “Меҳр” тушунчаси: фалсафий таҳлил. Science and Education, 3(4), 1312-1320.
7. Ro'zigul, B. (2023). TA ‘LIM TARBIYA JARAYONIDA INTERFAOL MEDOTLARDAN FOYDALANISH. ITALY" ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION IN THE FACE OF MODERN CHALLENGES"., 14(1).
8. Bozorova, R. Z., & Avezov, O. (2023). DINIY MASALALARDA TA'LIM-TARBIYANING AKS ETISHI. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(11), 153-156.
9. SHarofovna, B. R. Z. (2023). ILM NARSALARNING ENG FOYDALISIDIR. Научный Фокус, 1(6), 372-375.